

UNLOCKING MICROWAVE HEATING ON THE MOON: WHAT DO TEMPERATURE-DEPENDENT PERMITTIVITY MEASUREMENTS REVEAL ABOUT LUNAR REGOLITH?

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Introduction: Lunar regolith is a dielectric material which can be efficiently heated to melting temperature using microwave energy [1]. Sintered or melted regolith can then be used as feedstock to construct infrastructure on the Moon, including landing pads, roadways and habitats.

A material's real permittivity, ϵ' , and imaginary permittivity, ϵ'' , are important factors in determining the efficiency of microwave heating. For lunar regolith, these increase with temperature [2,3].

Temperature-dependent permittivity measurements made under microwave heating [3] have been found to differ notably from those made under furnace heating [2]. This suggests that the heating method influences permittivity measurements. Therefore, understanding the underlying mechanisms behind this behaviour will enable improved computational modelling and the optimisation of microwave heating processes.

Measurement of dielectric properties: In this study, a dual-mode technique was employed to enable simultaneous measurement of real and imaginary permittivity of lunar regolith simulants while heating approximately 2g of sample with 150W of microwave power close to 2.43GHz [4]. The mare simulant JSC-1A and highland simulant NU-LHT-4M were heated from ambient temperature to melting temperature at a rate of 0.25 °C/s under a nitrogen gas environment. Rapid changes in permittivity were measured instantaneously, with permittivity calculated using an enhanced Cavity Perturbation Method [4]. These results are compared with a furnace heating study of the same simulants, in which permittivity was measured using a CPM at 2.46 GHz for approximately 0.3g samples heated at less than 0.1 °C/s under argon [2].

Permittivity measurements: For both mare and highland simulants, the real and imaginary permittivity increased significantly with temperature, as shown in Figures 1 and 2. The permittivity measured via microwave heating was markedly higher than that measured under furnace heating.

After accounting for differences in density, the permittivity measured via microwave and furnace heating were similar at lower temperatures. For JSC-1A, microwave heating produced a more rapid increase in both ϵ' and ϵ'' than furnace heating from approximately 400 °C onwards, with the rate of in-

crease rising until the onset of melting, at which point both ϵ' and ϵ'' rose sharply.

NU-LHT-4M showed a markedly different response. Good agreement between microwave and furnace heating permittivity was observed at lower temperatures. However, near T_g , microwave heating caused a rapid, uncontrollable increase in permittivity, with a sharp rise in temperature. Both ϵ' and ϵ'' subsequently remained relatively constant, with DSC data indicating crystallisation of the glass phase in this temperature range [2], with a further sharp rise in ϵ'' indicating melting. By contrast, under furnace heating, ϵ' and ϵ'' increase only gradually up to approximately 1100 °C, after which both rose rapidly at the onset of melting.

Figure 1: Real and imaginary permittivity of JSC-1A as a function of temperature, microwave heating [3] compared with furnace heating [2]. T_g and T_m are from [2].

Figure 2: Real and imaginary permittivity of NU-LHT-4M as a function of temperature, microwave heating [3] compared with furnace heating [2]. T_g and T_m are from [2].

Discussion: The mechanisms of microwave heating are fundamentally different from those of furnace heating because they involve direct conversion of electromagnetic energy into thermal energy rather than heat transfer through thermal gradients.

As a result, microwave heated and furnace heated samples may not exhibit the same material state at the same bulk temperature, leading to differences in permittivity.

Absorbed microwave power is proportional to ϵ'' , so regions with higher dielectric loss heat preferentially. Consequently, in heterogeneous materials such as lunar regolith simulants, which contain phases with different dielectric properties, microwave heating is inherently non-uniform. The temperature sensitivity of permittivity, particularly at high temperatures, causes small increases in temperature to significantly amplify ϵ'' . This can lead to hotspot formation, localised thermal runaway and micro-melting [1]. In contrast, furnace heating is more likely to result in materials which are closer to thermal equilibrium. Non uniform heating is expected to have several consequences for the material response.

Above T_g , softened glass can promote liquid-phase sintering by wetting adjacent mineral grains and forming liquid bridges, thereby reducing porosity, enhancing densification and accelerating the sintering [5]. The resulting increase in density may contribute to the observed rise in permittivity, as previous studies have shown that the permittivity of regolith and regolith simulants increases with density [6,7,8]. Sample shrinkage observed by optical imaging during microwave heating above T_g , is consistent with such densification.

Lunar regolith simulants contain non-lunar phases that decompose during thermal processing, releasing volatiles such as H_2O and CO_2/CO . Carbonates such as $CaCO_3$, $CaMg(CO_3)_2$ and $FeCO_3$ are reported in NU-LHT-4M [9]. These decompose between 550-850 °C to form metal oxides. These defect rich oxides may increase the concentration of mobile charge carriers, enhance conduction-related dielectric losses and potentially contribute to the permittivity increase observed in NU-LHT-4M in this temperature range. Quantifying the influence of non-lunar phases on permittivity measurements is important for the design of accurate microwave heating processes.

At elevated temperatures, ϵ'' increases due to thermally activated conduction mechanisms. In addition, defects reduce the energy required for charge carrier generation [10], and the effects of material inhomogeneities and defects become more pronounced at higher temperatures [11]. In lunar regolith simulants, conduction mechanisms may include mixed-valence electron hopping (Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} and Ti^{3+}/Ti^{4+}) [12]. Electronic conduction in Al_2O_3 is also thermally activated and can produce a sharp increase in ϵ'' [10]. Given the higher relative abundance of Al_2O_3 compared to Fe and Ti bearing phases in NU-LHT-4M, this mechanism may contribute to the observed sharp increase in ϵ'' . Under microwave heating, these loss mechanisms couple directly to power absorption and may therefore drive further

rapid heating. Recent work has also suggested that microwave irradiation can drive redox reactions and increase electronic conductivity in oxide materials at temperatures lower than those required under furnace heating, indicating that electromagnetic fields may promote field assisted conduction processes in addition to thermal effects [13].

Because JSC-1A and NU-LHT-4M differ in mineralogical and chemical composition, the mechanisms responsible for the observed differences between microwave and furnace heating are also likely to differ, at least in part. Understanding the origins of permittivity increases, particularly large and rapid changes, is important for the design of controlled, energy efficient microwave processing systems, including cavity design. This will enable the exploitation of the advantages of microwave heating for ISRU in terms of both energy consumption and processing speed.

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